

ANALYSIS OF TYPES AND COMMUNICATION CHARACTERISTICS OF POLITICAL SPEECH

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Annotation: the introduction of this article provides general information about political speech, which is part of socio-political speech. The main part analyzes the types of political speech and their features.

Ключевые слова: политическая речь, политическая дискуссия, политическая дискуссия, лекция.

Аннотация: Во вводной части данной статьи дается обзор политической речи, являющейся частью общественно-политического дискурса. В основной части анализируются виды политической речи и их специфика.

Political speech is one of the earliest forms of public speaking. Because the emergence of oratory depends on political needs. If public speaking arose in connection with the needs of calling people to unity, encouraging patriotism or awakening the spirit of war in the period of early statehood, political speech began to take shape as a result of it. Before giving the meaning of political speech in public speaking, let us dwell on the essence of political speech. Political speech is defined in the text of the lectures "The Art of Oratory" by N. Goyibov, D. Yusobov, A. Mavlyanov as follows:

Mostly they are made by leaders and therefore are of a programmatic nature, such speeches reflect topical issues of the time, rich factual material.

In addition to these points, here is a commentary on political speech in the article "The Difference Between Political Speech and Commercial Speech" by Dr. Jennifer Müller, Lecturer in the Faculty of Law at Maurer University in India: Political speech is not just a speech developed by the authorities, but also a discussion of social problems. The main content of political speech explains the ways of the well-being of the people.

We will focus on the importance of public speaking, dividing political speech into three groups according to its content. Since political speech is not divided into groups and types in existing textbooks, we present the following classification as a recommendation for textbooks.

Political lectures. The word "lecture" is commonly used in two senses:

1. Oral or written information provided to a manager or supervisor. For example, "Written report of an official of a youth organization to the principal of the school on the fulfillment of holiday tasks."

2. Information provided to the public on a topic. In the second sense, speech is one of the forms of public speech and is written on various topics. Political lectures, which we study as the first type of political speech, also belong to the second meaning. Political speeches usually consist of political analyses, comments or assignments and plans.

Political discussions. Discussion is also a word borrowed from Arabic and has two meanings, like lectures: 1. To judge; 2. Reflection, conclusion

Political discussions consist of reflections and conclusions. Political discussions are mainly observed in Parliament and the Senate. In this process, the speaker is required to be able to defend his opinion, and not exclamations or appeals, as in political speeches. The importance of public speaking lies in the fact that in political discussions there is a diversity of opinions, and the improvisation of the speaker is also clearly manifested.

Political debate. Debate is also a concept close to discussion, and they are explained in the Explanatory Dictionary of the Uzbek Language as debates, disputes. Today, political debate is widespread in the global political arena and is referred to as "debate" in many countries. Basically, it is held before the elections and the relevance of the candidates' programs is assessed. By the number of participants in the debate, there are three of them: Karlpopper (named after the founder) - from three people, parliamentary debates - from two people, presidential debates - from one person. In debates, speakers are required not only to speak skillfully, but also to listen carefully. During the Q&A process, the way candidates answer questions will be judged separately. In oratory, a relatively new form of political speech, debates are of great importance, as they encourage and in a short time accustom speakers to right thinking.¹

As we noted above, political speech has a specific purpose. The level of realization of this goal directly depends on the correct organization of speech. In order for speech to be organized correctly, communicative students must respond to (correctness, accuracy, logic, purity of speech). Since political speech is made up of great opportunities and obligations, the satisfaction of each requirement integrates opportunities and obligations. Let's take a closer look at the communication requirements and their implementation:

Correctness of speech: "Correctness," writes V. G. Kostomarov, "as a necessary and first condition for the culture of speech, means strict and strict adherence to the norms of the literary language adopted at a certain time, its pronunciation, spelling, and it is necessary to understand and assimilate grammatical norms." Therefore, speech based on literary norms (lexico-semantic, pictorial, phonetic, accentological, grammatical, morphological and syntactic word-formation, spelling, stylistic, punctuation) can overcome the requirement of speech correctness. If we analyze political speech from the point of view of its audience, that is, if we take into account the characteristics of political speech for official circles, then we can say that "correctness of speech" is literally the first requirement for political speech. Because the obligation to follow the norms of the literary language in official circles is defined by law.

Clarity of speech. The requirement for speech accuracy is an integral continuation of the requirement for correctness and is a criterion that ensures the integrity of speech. Since speech consists of words, it acquires the form of a whole only when the words contained in it are used in their place, that is, when the requirement for clarity of speech is met. As we mentioned above, the content of political speech is determined by the fate of society, and each sentence in it must be correctly selected from synonymous lines and used in its place, paying attention to the aspects of polysemy and homonymy.

Purity of speech. If we think of a speech as a speaker's product, then this is the final review process before it goes on sale. In this process, foreign elements in its composition are

¹ Qudratov T., Nutq madaniyati asoslari. Toshkent: "O'qituvchi", 1993, 96-bet

removed. The level of purity of speech is assessed by the absence of parasitic words (frequently repeated), slang words, inappropriately used foreign words and phrases, slang, vulgarisms, clericalisms.

In a word, the purity of speech means, first of all, its compliance with the linguistic norms of the literary language. Any political speech should be free from the above elements. Because the meeting of various inappropriate repetitions or slang, vulgarity leads to a decrease in the political significance of speech.

In conclusion, we can say that the significance of political speech in eloquence can be seen not only in theoretical foundations, but also in practical processes. In the centuries-old history of mankind there are such political speeches that changed and renewed the destinies of an entire nation, the destinies of peoples, and their significance is visible not only in speech, but in all aspects of society.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar:

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